

Test Structure for the In-Plane Locations of Projected Features with Nanometer-Level Accuracy Traceable to a Coordinate Measurement System*

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SUMMARY

Manufacturing future generations of semiconductor devices through the year 2000 will require the overlay of successive patterns of material on wafers with accuracy and precision of the order of tens-of-nanometers. Feature placement metrology will need to operate at several times less than this, typically providing accuracy and precision at about the 10-nm level. Electrical test structures designed for determining feature placement have been shown to be capable of meeting *precision* requirements to the 2-nm precision level. This paper discloses a new test structure designed to measure the positions of the images of an array of features projected from a mask into a resist film on a substrate with *accuracy* better than 10 nm. The resist film on the substrate covers a nominally matching array of partially formed versions of the test structure prepatterned in a conducting film. Instances of the finished structure are formed on the substrate by further selective removal of conducting material from the partially formed test structures where they are overlaid by images of the fiducial marks on the mask. At each array point, the feature of the completed test structure that is defined by the overlay of the image of the fiducial marks on the mask is called the pointer. The part of the partially formed test structure that is unaffected by the overlay of the images of the fiducial marks on the mask serves as a ruler. Electrical testing accurately provides the precise location of the pointer relative to the ruler within each test structure. The locations of the rulers prepatterned on the substrate are determined with a Coordinate Measurement System (CMS) called the NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) Molecular Measuring Machine (M-Cubed).

For the purposes of illustrating the principles of the test structure, the results described in this paper were obtained from a two photo-step process that reduction-printed the complementary components of the test structure from two separate masks into a single resist film covering a previously unpatterned conducting film on a glass substrate.

A prime motivation for the development of the test structure is the rapid determination of the placement of the *images* of fiducial marks on the mask, as projected by the lithography tool, onto the substrate. One specific application is the low-cost, rapid, evaluation of image placement by X-ray lithography masks. Future applications include ultra-high-precision alignment, overlay, and image projection metrology at the single-digit nanometer level. This paper describes the new test structure and provides examples of preliminary measurements that indicate the required uncertainties of less than 10 nm appear to be attainable.

TRACEABILITY OF THE MEASUREMENTS

The locations F_{ij} of the rulers, constituted by the partially formed test structures prepatterned on the substrate prior to resist coating and exposure, are measured relative to the Cartesian grid points C_{ij} by

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M-Cubed, and are indicated by the circles with inscribed crosses in Figure 1. In turn, the C_{ij} are also located by M3 relative to global reference marks on the substrate. After post-exposure processing of the substrate, the locations \bar{P}_{ij} of the pointers, defined by the images projected from the mask, relative to the rulers of each respective test structure, are extracted by electrical testing. By this means, the array of partially formed test structures on the prepatterned substrate serves as a calibrated reference system. It allows the determination of the locations \bar{a}_{ij} , relative to the global reference marks on the substrate, to which the images of the fiducial marks are projected from the mask onto the substrate through the vector-addition process shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The positions of the projected images, relative to the precalibrated features on the substrate, are extracted electrically, thus providing the absolute positions of the latter.

The locations of the images of the fiducial marks projected from the mask onto the prepatterned substrate may be further traced back to provide the locations of the fiducial marks on the mask if the distortion and magnification of the projection system are known. The determination of these characteristics is the subject of a future application of the test structure.

THE NIST MOLECULAR MEASURING MACHINE

The locations of the features of the partially formed test structures on the prepatterned substrate, relative to the grid defined by the global reference marks in Figure 1, are determined by M-Cubed as shown in Figure 2. Based on a scanning tunneling microscope probe and the direct access which it provides to the geometry of single-crystal surfaces, state-of-the-art displacement interferometry, and advanced machine design, the M-Cubed system has been designed to position a scanning tunneling microscope probe and measure its location to an accuracy of 1 nm over an area of 50 by 50 mm [1]. M-Cubed is designed to enable the transfer of the metric and geometry of single-crystal surfaces into its metrology system and then to other

Figure 2. The NIST M-Cubed system positions its scanning tunneling microscope probe and measures its location to an accuracy of 1 nm over an area of 50 by 50 nm.

metrology prepatterned substrates such as a reference array for X-ray lithography. The M-Cubed system can accommodate prepatterned substrates of up to 85 mm in diameter by 12 mm thick or 125 mm in diameter by 5 mm thick. Limitations on the prepatterned substrate size are imposed by the dimensions of a ZERODUR[®]1 box which serves as the coordinate reference frame for M-Cubed's metrology system. Further details of M-Cubed are presented in a companion paper in this volume [2].

FUNDAMENTAL FEATURES OF THE NEW TEST STRUCTURE

The test structure introduced in this paper is an adaptation of the original Modified Offset Alignment Test Structure (MOATS) architecture [3], configured here specifically for the measurement of the local overlay vectors in two-stage lithography processes. It is the evolution of a concept which has so far been applied to single step processes only. In that particular application, which was the determination of feature placement accuracy by an electron-beam pattern generator, the fundamental active region of the test structure, a linear three-tap potentiometer bridge, resembled the geometry shown in the upper left of Figure 3, except that the center-tap had the same drawn width as the end-taps. The electrical properties of the intersections of all three taps to the bridge were required to be, and tested to be, identical. The potentiometer architecture allowed the determination of the location of the center-tap, relative to the two end-taps, with an uncertainty of less than 7 nm.

1. Certain commercial equipment, instruments, or materials are identified in this paper in order to specify the experimental procedure adequately. Such identification does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the National Institute of Standards and Technology, nor does it imply that the materials or equipment specified are necessarily the best available for the purpose.

Figure 3. Instances of the new electrical test structure are formed by selective removal of conducting material from the partially formed test structures where they are overlaid by images of the fiducial marks on the mask.

In the current work, a conducting film on the substrate is prepatterned at each array point with the potentiometer features shown schematically in the upper left of Figure 3. However, the wide center-tap seen there is subsequently modified by a superposed exposure of fiducial marks on the mask, shown in the upper right in Figure 3. This superposition ultimately results in selective removal of conducting material from the thicker prepatterned center-tap. The result is the center-tap shown in the lower part of Figure 3 and this is the pattern which is electrically tested.

It is important to note that, unlike the application described in [3], the center-tap junction to the bridge in the lower part of Figure 3 is different *physically*, and thus *electrically*, from the end-tap junctions to the bridge. For example, the drawing in the lower part of Figure 3 illustrates the indentation which is made into the bridge of the potentiometer by selective removal of material within regions defined by the images of the rectangular fiducial marks printed on the mask. This indentation avoids a requirement for perfect overlay in a direction perpendicular to the bridge during superposition of the rectangular marks on the mask onto the corresponding prepatterned potentiometer center-tap on the substrate during projection. Consequently, the center-tap, which is narrowed after processing, has an effective bridge-length-shortening parameter different from that of the end-taps. Thus physical tap separations derived from corresponding voltage measurements have to provide for two, generally different, bridge-length-shortening parameters compared to the single one in the previously reported single photo-step application[3].

ELIMINATION OF THE SYSTEMATIC ERRORS IN SINGLE PHOTO-STEP FABRICATION OF THE TEST STRUCTURE

The center-tap, which is narrowed after final patterning, not only has an effective bridge-length-shortening parameter different from that of the end-taps, but it also has a characteristic *displacement* different from that of the end-taps. In this context, the term *displacement* means the distance between the locations of the **geometrical center-line of the extended tap** from the **electrical center of the tap-to-bridge junction** in the direction of the length of the bridge, as illustrated in Figure 4. For fuller description of these terms, the reader is directed to Figures 5 and 6 and the text in [3].

Measurements have shown that differential electrical-center-to-

Figure 4. The electrical center of the center-tap is displaced (in the direction of current flow along the bridge) from the physical center-line of its extended length differently from the corresponding amounts in the end-taps.

physical-center displacement between the end- and center-taps, illustrated in Figure 4, can result in errors amounting to several hundred nanometers in the measurement of the lateral location of the center-tap relative to the end-taps if this differential displacement is not provided for by proper design of the structure. Specifically, the center- and end-taps must protrude from the same side of the bridge, which generally eliminates the *differential* displacement when the test structure is replicated in a single photo-step process. However, when measurements are extracted from test structures drawn with the same tap-width and bridge-width design rules located on the same substrate, the referenced errors are *constant* to within about 5 nm, as long as one other condition is satisfied. This condition is that the entire surface of the substrate is subjected to the same chemical and physical processing. In addition, regardless of the side of the bridge from which the center-tap protrudes, it must protrude from the same side relative to the end-taps on all the test structures [4].

The physical phenomenon responsible for differential displacement, described in [4], was hypothesized in that paper to be *asymmetric* Inside Corner Rounding (ICR). The hypothesis was substantially validated in modeling described in a later paper [5]. The last referenced paper also confirmed that the measurement offset was essentially constant on a particular substrate for particular design rules. However, [5] also showed that the measurement offset could also amount to several hundred nanometers between different substrates fabricated with *nominally* the same chemical and physical processing *even if the potentiometers were drawn with the same design rules*. In the single lithography exposure application, it has since been shown in [3] that all effects of the systematic offset error can be eliminated through an important modification of the test structure architecture involving cross-over tap-lines.

DISPLACEMENT ERRORS IN THE TWO PHOTO-STEP APPLICATION

In the single photo-step application, in which the end-taps and the center-tap are formed at the same time by the same processing, effects of the *systematic* offset error due to differential displacements between the center- and end-taps can be substantially reduced through the use of identical, cross-over, voltage lines for both kinds of tap. This design approach renders each of the two displacements

within the same test structure the same. In the two photo-step application, such an option does not exist because the center-tap junction to the bridge is necessarily formed in a different physical process from the one forming the end-taps. The fundamental problem in the two photo-step implementation is therefore the inherent and unavoidable *difference* of the displacements built into the center- and end-taps which generally results in an error in the determination of the location of the pointer due to the intra-test-structure differential displacement. No way has yet been reported that allows the determination of this quantity which at best is constant for a particular substrate and may typically have any value between zero and several hundred nanometers.

However, this particular application of the two photo-step test structure, which is to determine the separation of the pointers of two different potentiometers, renders the errors due to differential displacement inconsequential as long as the differential displacements of the two potentiometers is the same. This condition would normally be anticipated to prevail if the end-taps of both the potentiometers were fabricated at the same time, for example at the same exposure site, and that the center-taps were also fabricated simultaneously, even if this were in a different photolithographic process from that which formed the end-taps. That is, the differential displacements of the individual test structures are of no consequence as long as these differential displacements are the same for the two test structures.

Alternatively stated, the objective of the metrology is to determine the *self-referenced* placement of the potentiometer pointers. Thus, although the placement of any pointer relative to its end-taps *prepatterned* on the substrate *cannot* be determined at this time, the placement of any one pointer relative to any other *can* be determined as long as the fundamental requirement that the pointers and the end-taps each exhibit *translationally uniformity* of their inside corner-rounding.¹ Errors in the electrical measurement of the separation of the center-taps of a pair of potentiometers due to the difference of the differential displacements of the two potentiometers is hereafter referred to as the δt -effect error in the measurements of the separation of those pointers.

BRIDGE-LENGTH-SHORTENING PARAMETERS FOR THE TWO PHOTO-STEP APPLICATION

The other difference in this test structure from the previously reported test structures concerns the correction for finite tap widths [3]. Whereas previously the determination of only a *single* tap-induced bridge-length-shortening parameter δL was necessary, bridge-length-shortening in the two photo-step application is different for the end-taps from that for the center-tap.

Therefore, instead of the expression used in [3] and [4] for the single lithographic fabrication step for x_{MEAS} ,² which was

$$x_{MEAS} = \left(\frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1 + V_2} \right) \left(\frac{L - 2\delta L}{2} \right), \quad (1)$$

1. Again, it is *not* required that the ICR of the center-tap match that of the end-taps of either potentiometer and *vice versa*.
2. Where x is the difference from the lateral position of the center-line of the center voltage-tap and the center-point between the center-lines of the two end-taps per References [3] and [4]. (See also Figure 4 in this document.)

the appropriate expression for the distance x for test structures having non-zero differential displacement is

$$x_{MEAS} = \left(\frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1 + V_2} \right) \left(\frac{L - (\delta L_E + \delta L_C)}{2} \right) + \kappa \quad (2)$$

where δL_E and δL_C are the bridge-length-shortening parameters of the end- and center-taps, respectively, and κ is the effect of differential displacement for the particular set of design rules used to replicate the test structure. The method by which the two different δL parameters are extracted from local instances of the "dummy taps" follows the approach described in [3] and [4]. Of course, the other basic requirement for the extraction of reliable measurement of the separation of the pointers of two different potentiometers is that, in addition to their having equal differential displacements, each of the two δL parameters should also be the same for the two test structures.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST STRUCTURE AND TEST METHOD

For the purposes of illustrating the principles of the test structure, the results described in this paper were obtained from a two-photo step process that reduction-printed the complementary components of the test structure from two separate masks into a single resist film covering a previously unpatterned conducting film on a glass substrate. The overlay vectors determined from electrical testing were compared to those obtained by recycling the completed test structures through the coordinate measurement system for verification.

The substrate was arrayed with identical test chips defined from two digitized drawing levels. Level 1 played the role of the "Prepatterned Calibrated Substrate" and Level 2 served as the "Mask." For the purposes of evaluating the described metrology, each level was printed at 10X on separate chrome-on-glass photoplates with 0.1- μm pixel size to provide two separate but complementary optical stepper reticles. The 0.1- μm pixel size at 10X would not be normally necessary in the particular application proposed in this paper. This level of precision in primary pattern generation was employed in this case simply to facilitate the initial evaluation of the overall technique.

Figure 5. Each array point on the prepatterned substrate had a feature resembling the one shown here schematically. Certain dimensions that were selected for the prototype design are also shown.

Figure 6. The mask level pattern normally will not need all the features shown in this prototype architecture. Metal is removed from within regions on the prepatterned film on the substrate within the overlaying rectangles.

The partially completed test structure pattern replicated on the first, "Prepatterned Substrate," level is shown schematically in Figure 5. The design rules shown in the figure were not considered particularly important but merely matched those that had been used in earlier MOATS research. The multiple types of voltage-tap to bridge intersection shown in the upper part of the figure¹ were incorporated to expand the breadth of evaluation of the structure and not all would normally be used. The actual device geometry differed from the schematic in Figure 5 in that the part in the lower section, which was used for the extraction of the effective bridge-length-shortening parameters, had typically ten dummy end-tap/center-tap combinations rather than the lesser number shown here. Finally, the actual device layout geometry had voltage-tap geometries that were especially designed to facilitate comparison of distances extracted electrically with those measured by M-Cubed.

In the evaluation of the new two photo-step test structure, which is the basic subject of this paper, it was considered an unnecessary complication to provide for two-dimensional metrology. The evolution of the structure eventually to be used in applications will probably have a far less complex geometry and a smaller pad count. However, it will provide a two-dimensional metrology. Extending

Figure 7. After selective removal of metal film from the prepatterned substrate in regions defined by the overlaying rectangles, the resulting structure is ready for electrical testing.

the technique to do this is straightforward.

1. In the actual test structure, the section represented in the lower part of the figure was located directly to the left of the section shown in the upper part of the figure, as indicated by the broken line, and the composite structure with a single linear bridge was connected to a standard 2 by 16 padset, in a scheme similar to that otherwise indicated by the figure.

A key feature of the definition of the test structure is the selective removal of prepatterned conducting film from the substrate (Level 1, here) within regions demarcated by the overlaying rectangles of Level 2 on the "Mask" level, as illustrated in Figure 6. Of course, the mask level will not normally need all the rectangles shown in the prototype architecture in Figure 6. After selective removal of metal film from the prepatterned substrate in regions defined by the overlaying rectangles, the resulting structure shown in Figure 7 was ready for electrical testing on the working plate.

ARCHITECTURE OF THE TEST CHIP

An essential feature of the test chip architecture is shown in Figure 8. In Figure 8, the potentiometer bridge sections of two instances of the test structure are shown schematically as separated by a distance D . Corresponding potentiometers are internally calibrated for distances L_0 and L_n , respectively. The target of the metrology is to extract the distance S_{0n} , which corresponds to the separation of the images projected from the mask. Figure 8 shows

Figure 8. The measurements made by the CMS on the substrate may conveniently be made prior to the mask feature placement evaluation exposure. In any case, the location of images projected from the mask are determined as shown here.

how this is achieved by electrically extracting the center-tap placements, as defined by the mask-level rectangles, according to Eq. (2).

As previously indicated, the calibration of the prepatterned substrate in practice would normally be conducted prior to the modifications defined by the images on the mask. However, in the developmental work reported here, the distances D , L_0 , and L_n were conveniently determined by an optical CMS after the second exposure and the final patterning of the working substrate. This approach had the advantage of simultaneously allowing the electrical evaluations of Q_0 and Q_n to be compared directly with the numbers it provided. An early and limited selection of technical results is reviewed in the next section.

SAMPLE OF PRELIMINARY RESULTS

As shown previously, the two fundamental requirements for the successful utilization of the test structure shown in Figure 3 for positional metrology according to the scheme shown in Figure 8 are:

1. The end- and center-taps defined by images projected by the mask level onto the prepatterned substrate must be formed with *translationally uniform* inside corner-rounding at their intersections with the bridge to minimize the δt -effect errors described previously.
2. Each of the parameters δL_E and δL_C featured in Eq. (2) should also be the same for the two test structures whose relative placements are being measured.

The preliminary results presented in this section address these two specific issues and then show a sample of some remarkable comparisons of measurements of the separation of the pointers of pairs of potentiometers made electrically and by an optical CMS.

With regard to Requirement 1 above, Table 1 shows data, pertaining to δt -effect error magnitudes, extracted from two sets of three test structures within each of two exposure sites flashed onto the same substrate. The quantities "Intercept" in Table 1 were obtained statistically from a linear plot of the electrical location of the center-tap per Eq. (2), against the drawn location of the midpoint between the end-taps, for three drawn center-tap off-midpoint locations of -0.5 , 0.0 , and $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. These three drawn center-tap off-midpoint locations of course correspond to each of the set of the three test structures. The intercept value is essentially an estimate of the contribution to the δt -error for that exposure site, modified by any

Table 1. Examples of errors resulting from the δt effect and provisionally attributed to translational nonuniformities of ICR.

Test Structure Set	Intercept (μm)		Residual Error
	1	2	
First Exposure Site	0.1559	0.1560	0.1 nm
Second Exposure Site	0.0847	0.0913	6.6 nm

actual misalignment of the mask level to the substrate level which may be present for the exposure site where the test structures are located. However, since the contribution to the intercept value made by the site exposure misalignment is normally expected to be constant for a particular site,¹ the quantities labeled "Residual Error" in Table 1 give an indication of the size of the δt effect which could contribute to the overall error in the measurement of the separation of pairs of potentiometer pointers at that exposure site. Since the actual numbers presented in Table 1 are extracted from the *drawn* locations of the pointers relative to the end-taps, any errors generated by drawn misplacement of the pointers are *included*. Thus the numbers presented suggest that the δt errors will indeed be tolerable as the technique is developed in the future.

The data in Table 1 suggest that the potential contributions of δt -effect errors amount for the first site to about 0.1 nm and, for the second site, to about 6 nm. Based on this first and limited data set, placement metrology errors of somewhere between zero and 10 nm appear to have occurred in the measurement of the separation of pairs of pointers as a result of nontranslational uniformity of inside corner rounding from test structure to test structure within the individual exposure sites. Alternatively said, errors resulting from nonuniformity of inside corner rounding seem to be contributing no

1. This may not be the case if there is a rotational misalignment of the exposure site.

more than 10 nm to the proposed pointer-to-pointer metrology.

The other fundamental requirement, listed as Requirement 2 at the beginning of this section, also seems to have been satisfied. Table 2 lists the extracted values of the two effective bridge-length-shortening parameters, δL_E and δL_C in Eq. (2), for six test structures at each of four locations. The end-tap parameters are all within about two tenths of a micrometer. This range converts into about 2-nm loss of positional accuracy in the determination of the location of the center-tap for the 20- μm -long potentiometer bridges that were used here. This is considered to be acceptable. The uniformity of the center-tap results for δL_C within a test site is of welcome significance because there was no way of knowing how well the requirement for constancy of the δL_C -values would be met before the actual measurements were made. It is anticipated that the δL_C should be negative since their effect is to *extend*, rather than to *shorten* the bridge length. Whereas the end-tap effective bridge-length-shortening parameters, δL_E , are quite uniform across the substrate, as also would be anticipated, the center-tap effective bridge-length-shortening parameters, δL_C , are only constant within a particular exposure site, again as might be expected, although the cause of the site-to-site variations needs further study. Intra-site uniformity alone is required for the proposed metrology.

Table 2. The values of δL extracted from six test structures at each of four test chip sites show uniformity adequate for the purposes of 10- μm positional metrology.

Chip	T-S	δL (μm)	
		End-tap	Center-tap
3,3	A	0.393	-1.442
	B	0.273	-1.550
	C	0.424	-1.692
	D	0.483	-1.601
	E	0.335	-1.411
	F	0.413	-1.478
4,3	A	0.445	-2.443
	B	0.415	-2.487
	C	0.415	-2.117
	D	0.211	-2.513
	E	0.556	-2.360
	F	0.396	-2.249
3,4	A	0.446	-1.759
	B	0.339	-1.712
	C	0.338	-1.974
	D	0.512	-1.810
	E	0.514	-1.516
	F	0.346	-1.797
4,4	A	0.562	-2.717
	B	0.337	-2.555
	C	0.361	-2.380
	D	0.405	-2.468
	E	0.369	-2.518
	F	0.345	-2.209

A preliminary sample of results of the determination of intra-chip

Table 3. Examples of comparisons of electrical and optical CMS measurements of the parameter s in Figure 8. All dimensions are in micrometers.

Reference	Electrical	Optical CMS	Difference
F to F1	2687.523	2687.434	-0.005
F to F2	5375.127	5375.094	0.042
F to F3	8100.025	8099.978	0.059
F to F4	10787.447	10787.413	0.036
F to F5	13475.156	13475.072	0.096

pointer-to-pointer distances s in Figure 8, is shown in Table 3, indicating accuracies of the order of tens of nanometers over distances of up to 13 mm. This limited sample of early results from the first prototype implementation of the metrology scheme strongly suggests its future potential, and research is continuing to further develop this metrology.

CONCLUSIONS

The robust electrical test structure metrology proposed in this paper for the rapid and low-cost measurement of the placement of images of features from a mask onto a substrate has two major requirements. Whether these requirements would be met in typical practice was not previously known and has now been investigated. The result is that they have been met to the extent that they appear to contribute no more than 10 nm to errors in the measurements extracted from a single-exposure site on the substrate. A further outcome of this first implementation of the technique indicates that feature separations of up to 13.5 mm, printed on a substrate, have been measured electrically to within 30 to 90 nm. Although this is a noteworthy result, there are numerous known factors that are considered to be manageable by refinements to enable the reduction of these errors to the 10-nm level with further experience. This is the subject of ongoing and future research in the area.

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